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Preface

In this age and time, capturing ‘state of the art’ of computing in a conference proceedings gets to be increasingly hard. It is quite common too for the submitted abstracts to refer to studies yet to be done – and the time span between abstract submission and the actual conference is often less than six months. By the time the proceedings appear in journal form, a similar period after its closing session, some of the work is over a year old, by which time new ideas will have been formed and the deployment of current ones progressed – at times beyond recognition.

Still in the long term these journal papers, more than the actual software or collected data sets, will likely be what is preserved for future generations. Although curation of journal papers, books, and what we today consider cultural heritage may be fraught with problems, these sources of information – condensed forms of knowledge – have a highly experienced community of experts from the library and archival world behind them who now enthusiastically embrace ‘digital cultural heritage’. These include sanctuaries where digital data can safely reside without being connected to the (by now almost ubiquitous) internet. But preserving our physics data in HEP is more challenging than merely archiving our publications. ‘Keeping the bits’ might be rather costly, but is at least a conceptually tractable problem. But understanding what the bits mean, and having the capabilities to process the data using the original tools requires much study yet to be undertaken. Describing the data, programs, and algorithms such that future physicists can understand how to reproduce the results is decidedly hard; and we can just hope that the fact that no contributions on (software) documentation were submitted to this CHEP is incidental.

The programme, list of participants – and of course the proceedings – of the first CHEP conference have been preserved: in 1985 Prof Dr Bob Hertzberger of the computer science department of the University of Amsterdam (but having worked in high-energy physics for a long time) together with Prof Dr Walter Hoogland of Nikhef brought together a unique mix of physicists, computing scientists, systems engineers and key industrial developers discussing presenting the then-latest developments in embedded systems, vector and parallel processing, and networking. It was the start of a successful series of CHEP conferences across the whole world. Looking back in 2013, twenty editions later, some of these topics have faded into history: the portability aspects of Modula-2 are today no longer relevant; VAX systems, having served us faithfully for many years, have become museum pieces; and satellite communications would incur unacceptable latency and bandwidth limitations in today’s voluminous data age – although a future space-based experiment like LISA will obviously be the exception to the rule of fibre-optic networks. But many topics still deserve our attention, or have in the last few years re-gained much of their relevance. It is both interesting and worrisome to realise that most of the vector (nowadays relabelled as ‘GPU’) and parallel processing experience and knowledge of the 1980’s and early 1990’s for a long time lay dormant. In the early 90’s it was part and parcel of many a bachelor programme – as a physicist one was supposed to be versed in optimization and systems architecture. Most of that 1st CHEP conference was dedicated to parallel (co)processors and SIMD-SPMD systems. However, the unprecedented increase in CPU clock speed and single-core performance lulled us to sleep in the later 90’s and many now have to learn anew

much of what we thought we knew. But at the same time we now go much beyond that, and we hope the papers of CHEP2013 show you the future both in terms of massive multi-core computing and in data parallelism.

With this 20th CHEP we continue the inclusive model that brings together physicists, computer scientists, and computing and data engineers with a wide diversity of expertise and from many branches of sub-atomic physics. These proceedings include papers from both large ‘general-purpose’ physics experiments as well as from highly specialised work on the frontier of precision and intensity. From data acquisition at -40 °C under the ice in the Antarctic to the management of data from optical sky surveys looking for dark energy. From improving power efficiency of Monte-Carlo event generation to the impact of merging processing, memory, and optical networking onto a single chip; with papers on massively parallel processing, and with papers on massive parallel disk stores; on the engineering of software, networks, and on the data centres in which it all resides.

What this shows most clearly is that ‘data infrastructure’ and ‘information technology’ today are as much a piece of the experimental apparatus as detectors, magnets, and accelerators. Computing, including all of its engineering aspects, is in and of itself a challenging research topic, both of a fundamental and applied character – and deserves to be credited as such. The high-energy and nuclear physics community has traditionally been blessed with excellent people devoting their career (and quite often their entire life) to the advancement of computing as a scientific instrument. Ever since that first CHEP conference in 1985 hundreds if not thousands of physicists, computing scientists and engineers have created and maintained a vibrant field. On the one hand, this can and ought to serve as an example for many other fields of research that are faced with large data volumes or complex collaborations. Yet at the same time also our CHEP community should keep its eyes open to the world: often wildly innovative and disruptive innovation comes from places unlooked-for. And we have reached a scale where the next step must by necessity be a collaborative step: data and computing are a basic infrastructure of all of research, across disciplines, countries, and continents. If we want to sustain our growing data needs in the future, we should leverage this shared common IT infrastructure and give it our support.

The sheer size of this volume can be considered a testament to the fact that our community is very much alive and thoroughly enthusiastic. We were blessed with a very forward-looking group of experts in our international advisory committee. The excellent work of the programme committee, who not only put together the technical tracks of the conference but also edited the various sections of this Proceedings journal, demonstrates that many are ready to devote their precious time to the advancement of computing. It is hard to even begin to express our gratitude to all those who worked hard to make CHEP2013 a success: over 500 participants, almost a similar number of submissions, and well over 300 papers have been processed by a programme committee of less than 40 people. You will see their names in this journal as editors of their respective sections – which correspond to the six parallel tracks of the conference. Our thanks go to them as guardians of these proceedings and for carefully constituting the parallel programme of the conference itself.

After 28 years and 20 editions CHEP is ‘going strong’ and continues expanding to cover new ground as our field develops. Our history bodes well for the future, as the University of Tokyo and KEK – together with RIKEN, OIST, and Osaka University – organise the next CHEP conference from April 13–17, 2015, in Okinawa, Japan.

Amsterdam, March 2014,

David Groep, Conference Chair

Daniele Bonacorsi, Programme Chair